

Commons, coppices and cork oak cultivation vs sustainability

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Introduction

After more than 20 years of continuous commitment to the management of the forest commons in the municipality of Senghe, a small town in the central-western part of Sardinia, the following notes aim to document the efforts and to project the work into the next decades.

The title is more general, because the experience is about a social and ecological context that represents very well the conditions that can be found in many other places, in Sardinia and beyond. Nevertheless, the fact that we have not been so deeply confronted with other such circumstances has to be taken into account.

The plural subject in the narrative needs to be commented. The work began around 2004 as a university project, implemented by a group of associated young forest professionals. The project initiated the process that we will describe and a strong relationship with the local community. Beyond the project, the relationship kept me as a university reference, but especially Dr Cristian Ibba, as the living heart of the system, in contact with the community and thus with the many different municipal administrations that have succeeded in these decades, as stewards of the management of the biennial wood gathering in the commons. This experience would not have been possible without Dr. Ibba's dedication.

The development of the text aims at presenting the various specific questions in a robust overarching framework, and therefore it goes back to issues that are well known, but connected in terms that may not be sufficiently focused.

Sustainability and the paradigm shift

The sustainability of our way of life is deeply in question. We share a perception of (and much factual data on) the unsustainability of the current way of consuming the environment but we do not share, in practice, a strategy to try to avoid worsening the situation (Pereira and Funtowicz 2020).

It is evident that the extraordinary improvement of the living conditions of a relevant part of the world's population that the technological development achieved has been fueled by the confidence in a 'positive' future. But, on the other hand, the environmental costs of many

improvements, though with delay, have become more and more evident, stimulating further improvements to avoid or correct those environmental impacts. What is less evident is the vicious circle that the process can and has frequently activated. This aspect is much less evident because it depends on the 'glasses' through which one looks at it.

A minimal example concerning agriculture can help shed some light. Take vineyard cultivation, in a typical hilly landscape. The traditional technology, limited by what could be achieved with animal traction, was forced to build dry stone retaining walls to obtain terraces contouring the slope where vine rows were aligned on surfaces not too steep for the oxes to work. Technological advancement introduced mechanical tractors, that would work much better along the maximum gradient. Stone walls were dismantled and vine rows planted aligned along the slope descent, possibly uninterrupted. Tractors could work safely and efficiently but, also water erosion becomes much more efficient, determining beyond the direct negative impact on the vineyard, more general losses due to solid matter transportation (Bordoni, M., Persichillo, M. G., et al. 2017) and biodiversity (Böhm et al. 2024). The correction, reflecting the faith in the power of the reductionist approach, consists in using more powerful machines to ground capable drainage systems and, eventually, supplement the nutrients deficiencies with fertilizers. The problem, at least in the short to the mid term perspective, is solved for the vineyard, but for the environment of the territory all negative impacts are just displaced.

Un-sustainability is actually an evidence of the insufficiency of the -still widespread- view that considers the world as a mechanism that can be understood (and governed) isolating and reducing it to ever finer parts.

That corrections developed within such a frame of mind can and have activated vicious circles of this kind is easily seen in all contexts. In this sense the paradigm shift towards system thinking (Capra and Luisi 2014) has to be acknowledged as a prerequisite to approach sustainability discourses (Voulvoulis et al. 2022). As a matter of fact, this shift is deeply implemented at many levels of the decision making processes, from the UN Sustainable Development Goals down to, as will be mentioned later, the recent Italian law concerning the commons, but it is not sufficiently acknowledged, it has not yet been acquired as a reference within the general culture.

System thinking actually implies reversing the way we perceive reality. Things are no longer isolated pieces of matter, rather a complex nested composition of relations and interactions, with a tremendous impact on science, that has to rebuild its epistemic foundation, and on society: no way to escape from the need to take individual (and collective) responsibility.

Just to conclude the vine yards cultivation example, corrections framed in the context of the cultural landscapes (Farina 2000) have been implemented, rebuilding dry stone retention walls that, as an evolution of the cultural heritage, attempt to re-synchronize that environmental know-how with societal needs and financial constraints (Socci et al. 2019). But, presenting such valuable efforts as geared to obtain "multiple ecosystem services" does not acknowledge the paradigm shift that actually is behind the investment!

Commons and forest commons ('estovers')

In English traditional culture, the commons was defined as land or resources managed collectively by a defined community, with each member holding specific, customary rights of use, rather than absolute ownership. These rights included, for example: grazing livestock (common of pasture), collecting wood or brush (common of estovers), cutting turf for fuel (common of turbary), fishing in streams (common of piscary), gleaning leftover crops after

harvest. This arrangement was foundational in many rural communities for centuries and was distinct from both private property and open-access land (Short 2008).

Globally, commons are distributed in diverse forms, from traditional irrigation and grazing lands in rural communities to fisheries and forests managed by indigenous or local groups. Forests are a central component of these 'common-pool resources' (CPR).

Western economies have indeed made significant efforts to dismantle or privatize commons all over the world, often treating them as a heritage burden that hinders resource optimization. Commons were considered an "imperfect property" (Todde, 1882, voce 'Ademprivio' in "Enciclopedia giuridica italiana", IN: Todde, Maurandi, and Todde 2003, 36). "The tragedy of the Commons" (Hardin 1968) represents the most renowned emergence of an iceberg dating back before the 17th century and still operating. Enclosures are well known in Britain (around year 1800) as well as in Sardegna ('Una riforma zoppa in Sardegna: l'Editto delle chiudende (Ferrai Cecilia)' 2019) were, as an example, the "su connottu" uprising against the "prinzipales" took place in Nuoro on the 26th of April 1868.

Elinor Ostrom documented that correctly governed CPR are of fundamental value for the territory. With her lifelong research work, applying a systems approach (Ostrom 1996), she won the Nobel prize in 2009, having provided a fundamental contribution to reverse, at a worldwide level, the attitude and perception concerning the commons.

In Italy CPRs are very widespread, governed and characterised in many different ways. The '*usi civici*' are a specific Italian legal and cultural form of CPR involving collective use rights on land owned by others, very frequently by the municipality. Such rights, grounding far back in history, are bound to: inalienability, inusucapibility and imprescriptibility. Moreover, these rights of use are very specific in nature. The survival of the peasants was in the interest of the landlord: by securing these rights, he could ensure the productivity of the land and his own well-being. This origin is reflected in the fundamental prohibition of (private) commercial use of commons production.

The main Italian law governing "usi civici" is Law No. 1766 of 1927, dating back to pre-republic times. It regulates, uniformly across Italy, two types of rights in favor of communities: rights of use over land owned by others ('*jura in re aliena*', which corresponds to "*usi civici*" in the strict sense) and ownership of land by the community ('*jura in re propria*'). The law, reflecting the perspective of the time, provides for the liquidation of the "*usi civici*"!

The Italian republican constitution (1948), though having discussed on how to take CPRs into consideration, finally recognized only two ownership forms: public and private.

The paradigm shift began to take effect at the end of the last century.

The "Cultural Heritage and Landscape Code (Legislative Decree 42/2004)", recognizing the environmental, historical, and cultural value of "*usi civici*" as an expression of collective identity and landscape conservation, defines their protection status as environmental values and cultural heritages.

More recently, thanks to the lifelong commitment of Professors Paolo Grossi and Pietro Nervi to the reversal of the perception of CPR, a new law (law no. 168 of 2017) has been promulgated. In a systems approach framework, elaborating on the constitutional articles that define and defend the social dimension of land tenure, this law profoundly modifies the evaluation of the CPRs (although it does not repeal the law of 1927!). It does encourage the "commoners" to establish a legal entity ('*ente esponenziale*') in order to autonomously govern their CPR establishing a live link with the paradigm shift that sustainability implies: the need to take up personal and collective direct responsibility for land stewardship.

Coppicing, silviculture, land stewardship and the community

Coppicing is the forest management system that relies on the vegetative regrowth from stumps or roots stimulated by cutting the trees or the shoots, in suited species (and conditions). The system has a long history and a significant presence primarily in Europe, especially in the Mediterranean region, though it is practiced on a smaller scale in northern countries and, more or less informally, all over the world since wood is still the most used renewable energy source worldwide ('Firewood Market by Wood Type, End-User, Distribution Channel: Global Opportunity Analysis and Industry Forecast, 2021-2031' 2023).

In Italy and namely in Sardegna, historical evidence of coppicing practices are widespread and date back to the roman times; the Italian word for coppice is 'ceduo' a direct derivation of the latin 'caeduus': "that can be cut", periodically. Archaeological researches trying to answer the question "how did the Nuragic people produce the energy needed to melt bronze and other metals?" are not yet available. The industrial revolution invested Sardegna developing mines (that required extensive coppice cultivation, see the Marganai example) and extending forest exploitation both for the production of railroad sleepers and charcoal. The area in figure 1 is part of Seneghe commons forest in 1954. The density of the charcoal kilns testifies the relevant exploitation level and the spread of the coppices in the area at that time.

Figure 1 - Aerial photo of part of Seneghe forest in 1954

When gas and petrol for heating and cooking reached Sardinia, some decades later than on the mainland, coppicing declined. At the same time, justified to a certain extent by the many cases of overexploitation of the forests (through coppicing, but not only), the State Forestry corp, responsible for ensuring the environmental protection function of the forests, together with the forestry schools, pressed for the conversion of the coppices into high forests.

The criticism of coppicing, which was founded in the decades after the Second World War, is still present, although the original motivation is no longer there. Some forestry thinkers (inside and outside of academia) share with some 'environment protection' associations and practitioners the negative valuation of this renewal method as a primeval practice and find it alarming that in the last decades coppicing has resumed. Forest owners, forestry operators and commoners that earn part of their living on firewood, taking appropriate attention in the operations, together with other forestry thinkers and environment protectors, find coppicing practical and, on the whole, environmentally bearable.

Can coppicing be part of a sustainable forest management?

Including coppicing among the silvicultural regeneration practices is questionable, it exposes the foresters to a justified criticism: the practice tends to favor the perpetuation of the existing gene pool rather than the generation of new combinations. A distinct category should be introduced reflecting the fact that the new forest will be made mainly by shoots with a reduced introduction of new genes, with obvious consequences on the "system's autopoiesis", the capacity of the forest to adapt to the changing environment.

This entails that coppice cultivation involves some inevitable environmental costs and many different impacts that are more or less severe depending on the specific site characteristics and exploitation techniques employed (from soil compaction or exposition to erosion, to damages by the mechanical means) and that can be more or less limited or compensated adopting suited precautions like well designed extraction lines and access routes or the creation and distribution of aging groups.

Given its inevitable costs, the sustainability assessment of coppicing, like that of any wheat crop, must take into account the great responsibility it entails. Every two years, new exploitation patches are cut. The distribution and design of these patches creates the structural diversification and dynamism of the landscape that can be an expression of the community's commitment to land stewardship. A significant contribution to community identity and its temporal projection is also the kind of social gathering that takes place in the forest during the exploitation season. By taking into account the territorial system as a whole, that is, the different components of the community and of the forest, the question of sustainability can be addressed in a proper way and possibly with a positive evaluation. "Is the availability of firewood that the practice produces meaningful at community level? (in financial, social and environmental terms)", "Would livelihood in Seneghe be better refraining from the exploitation?", "Is the community taking up the responsibility required by the care the management needs?", are examples of questions to be considered.

This last one is an example of a question which, in Senghe's case, does not yet have a positive answer. Efforts undertaken in these years to encourage Seneghe commoners to shape and establish an '*ente esponenziale*' (the autonomous institution that the law on 'usi civici' foresees to actively govern these CPRs) produced some increase in the population awareness but no tangible effect. Thus, the responsibility for the management of the forest commons still lies with the municipality, which cannot be a good manager of the forest because it is not an institution designed for this purpose and, in addition, it has to respond to its natural five-year electoral cycle.

Cork oak, ecology, silviculture and cork extraction management

Following the last Italian forest inventory, Sardinia's cork oak stands cover approximately 140,000 to 186,000 hectares according to the Italian National Forest Inventories (Gasparini et al. 2022) and related regional data ('Guida Alla Commercializzazione Del Sughero in Campo' 2013), representing over 80% of Italy's cork oak forest area. EU-funded reforestation has added 5,000–10,000 hectares of new cork oak plantations in recent decades. Cork oak trees are also present, as non-dominant species, or even as isolated individuals (though generally exploited for cork production) in stands dominated by other oaks (holm oak, downy oak) or in mixed macchia formations.

In Sardinia, *Quercus suber* dominates two main vegetation series and is mentioned in other two series, all on acid soils ('Piano Forestale Ambientale Regionale - All. II. Descrizione Delle Serie Di Vegetazione' 2007). These cork oak woodlands are shaped by ecological dynamics such as succession, grazing, and fire, which influence their structure and biodiversity. Human activities like livestock grazing and shrub clearing, along with recurring fires, play a crucial role in maintaining or altering these habitats.

The complexity of the frame concerning cork oak silvicultural management is already evident with just these few data. Interactions dominate the scene. Attempts to study the theme isolating cork oak do not provide any concrete contribution (Corona et al. 2018; Vogiatzakis, Griffiths, and Zomeni 2020; La Riccia et al. 2023).

Other sources (Sanna, Re, and Franca 2015), focusing on agroforestry, state that Sardinian cork oak forests cover ~20% of the island (493,352 ha), with small private plots (10-20 ha) dominating production and specialized labor practices for cork stripping. Annual cork output reaches 17,000-20,000 tons, generating ~€150M/year primarily through bottle stoppers (60-70% of output).

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<con la '**selvicoltura più vicina alla natura**'>

... in assenza di una relativa risoluzione, **le classiche aporie della cultura forestale**, rappresentate dalle antitesi tra uomo e natura, economia ed ecologia, teleonomia e teleologia, e precipitate nell'antinomia tra "bosco normale" e "bosco reale", **rimangono stabilmente in piedi**, così fatalmente **mantenendo una intrinseca estraneità tra le attività dell'uomo e le dinamiche naturali**

...

la **Selvicoltura Sistemica**, con i suoi espliciti contorni etici ed epistemologici, **si è incaricata di affrontare la questione forestale nel suo complesso, manifestando nell'obiettivo dell'armonia sistemica**, sancito dai diritti del bosco, e nel corrispettivo metodo della epistemologia della complessità, **i caratteri di una raggiunta coincidenza tra selvicoltura e natura**. In essa trova composizione l'aporia centrale e riassuntiva della cultura forestale, rappresentata dall'antinomia tra economia ed ecologia,